

RECOVERY OF ELEMENTARY SULPHUR FROM GASES CONTAINING SULPHURETTED HYDROGEN

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For the recovery of elementary sulphur from waste gases, action of iron oxide as adsorbent for H_2S has been tested. Incorporation of Al_2O_3 and MnO_2 has been found to increase the activity of the adsorbent.

India's consumption of sulphur in normal times was of the order of 30,000 tons per year and it has been estimated that about 10,000 tons (*i.e.*, one third of the total consumption) of recoverable sulphur are lost annually in the various coke-ovens in India. In view of the position of sulphur in India and its great economic importance in industrial operations, it was thought desirable to investigate the possibility of recovering elementary sulphur from these gases (which are normally poor in sulphurous constituents).

Development of the newer wet processes for the purification of these gases (*e.g.* Thylox process using alkaline solution of arsenious oxide, Gluud's still process using ferric hydroxide mud, Otto process using ferricyanides, Gorbital process using mono- and triethanolamine, Phenolate process using alkaline solution of phenols, etc.), has not been able to do away with the dry processes involving the use of oxide of iron, luxmasses, activated carbon etc. In the case of gases comparatively poor in H_2S content, the dry processes are generally utilised. These processes, are, therefore, of special importance in India where the coals and consequently the industrial gases, are, on the whole, poorer in sulphur content (Assam and Punjab coals have, however, high content of sulphur).

In the present investigation, we have studied the action of iron oxide as adsorbing agent for H_2S and have been able to increase its activity by incorporating alumina or oxide of manganese. Adsorbing capacity of activated carbon was also found to increase by incorporating it with alumina. Though the activity of activated carbon was found to be somewhat less than either of alumina and iron oxide and oxide of manganese and iron oxide, it can be used effectively in the case of gases containing organic sulphur. The amount of sulphur actually recovered by extraction from various adsorbing agents has been determined and the adsorbents have, then, been revived to almost their original activity.

EXPERIMENTAL

For this study, an artificial mixture of the following composition by volume, was used :

H_2 = 50% ; CO = 45% ; H_2S = 2 to 3% ; N_2 = traces ; O_2 = traces.

Preparation of Adsorbents.—The various adsorbents were prepared as follows:—

1. Ferric hydroxide, prepared by adding 1.5*N*-ammonia solution to ferric chloride solution containing 6.3 g. of Fe_2Cl_6 per 100 c.c.
2. Mixed Fe_2O_3 — Al_2O_3 adsorbent was obtained by mixing various proportions of aluminium sulphate solution containing 4.95 g. of $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ per 100 c.c., to a fixed amount of the above mentioned ferric chloride solution and precipitating the same by 1.5*N*-ammonium hydroxide.
3. Mixed Fe_2O_3 — MnO_2 adsorbent was prepared as above. Manganese sulphate containing 10.97 g. of MnO_2 per 100 c.c. being taken in place of aluminium sulphate.
4. Mixed activated carbon (Kahlbaum)— Al_2O_3 was prepared by suspending 10 to 15 g. of activated carbon in the aluminium sulphate solution and precipitating the same by stock ammonia solution.

5. Mechanical mixtures of different adsorbents were made by mixing different amounts of constituents intimately in a mortar.

In all the above cases the adsorbents, before each experiment, were maintained at particle size of 4.5 mm. to 3 mm.

Procedure.—The experimental gas was collected in an aspirator bottle over concentrated solution of sodium chloride, from which it was passed through dry fused calcium chloride. The passage was regulated with a screw clip and the gas passed through three U-tubes in series containing definite quantities of adsorbents. The gas was then passed through two guard vessels and finally bubbled through dilute solution of lead acetate. The passage of gas was stopped as soon as the colouration was seen in lead acetate vessel and the first U-tube weighed in order to find out the amount of sulphuretted hydrogen adsorbed. A fresh tube charged with adsorbent was introduced in place of the third U-tube at the end of the series so that the middle tube came in place of the first and was saturated before being weighed. In this way the saturation point of the adsorbent with regard to H_2S was found out. The following tables give the results of preliminary investigations.

TABLE I

Adsorbent used:—Mechanical mixture of Fe_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 dried at 95° to 100° in a current Fe_2O_3 of dry air for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hrs. Rate = 20 bubbles per minute. H_2S in gaseous mixture = 2.4% by volume.

Al_2O_3 in the adsorbent.	Sulphur content		Al_2O_3 in the adsorbent.	Sulphur content	
	Average increase in wt.	Sulphur estimated by fusion method.		Average increase in wt.	Sulphur estimated by fusion method.
0%	25.55%	25.70%	37.5%	28.03%	28.16%
11.5	25.987	25.90	41.2	24.02	24.00
20.1	35.03	34.80	60.0	17.45	17.00
28.5	30.935	31.11	100	0.395	0.36
33.3	29.04	29.50			

TABLE II

Adsorbent used:—Mechanical mixture of Fe_2O_3 and MnO_2 , dried at 95° to 100° . H_2S in the gas = 2.91% by vol.

MnO_2 in the mixed adsorbents.	Sulphur content	
	Average increase in wt.	Sulphur estimated by fusion method.
0%	25.55%	25.70%
7	27.4	27.12
13	32.05	31.79
20	29.47	29.15
100	2.20	2.11

It will be observed that addition of 20.1% Al_2O_3 or 13% MnO_2 increases the amount of adsorption of H_2S in Fe_2O_3 from 25.7 to 34.8% or 31.79%.

Optimum Composition of Mixed Adsorbents

Mixed adsorbents, prepared by simultaneous precipitation of Fe_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 from solution, are likely to give better results. Moreover, the water content in the adsorbent at the time of its use is likely to prove an important factor in the adsorption.

The following results were obtained when experiments were performed with a view to finding out the optimum composition of various mixed adsorbents and their optimum temperature of activation.

TABLE III

Adsorbent used: Fe_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 , formed by simultaneous precipitation, and activated at $230\text{--}35^\circ$ for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours, H_2S in gaseous mixture being 2.65% by volume.

Al_2O_3 in adsorbent	Sulphur content	
	Average increase in wt.	Sulphur estimated (fusion method)
0.0%	25.54%	25.70%
19.47	48.06	47.82
25.11	56.98	56.83
29.83	54.80	54.10
38.79	52.61	51.68
100.0	0.395	0.36

TABLE IV

Adsorbent used: Mixed adsorbent containing Fe_2O_3 and MnO_2 obtained by simultaneous precipitation, and activated at $230\text{--}35^\circ$ for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hrs., H_2S in the gaseous mixture being 2.12% by volume.

MnO_2 in the mixed adsorbents.	Sulphur content	
	Average increase in wt.	Sulphur estimated by fusion method.
0.0%	25.55%	25.7%
20.30	44.31	43.46
30.84	47.98	47.18
34.82	54.72	53.98
40.10	52.09	52.00
100	2.20	2.11

TABLE V

Adsorbent used: Activated charcoal incorporated with Al_2O_3 , temperature of activation being $230\text{--}35^\circ$, the percentage of H_2S being 2.43 by volume.

Al_2O_3 in the mixed adsorbents.	Sulphur content	
	Average increase in wt.	Sulphur estimated by Eschka method.
100.0%	0.395%	0.36%
18.68	41.80	37.74
14.20	42.40	39.24
9.28	48.67	43.98
4.85	45.47	41.12
0	43.67	38.28

It will be seen that in the case of all the adsorbents used, incorporation of Al_2O_3 had decidedly an augmenting effect, the increase being maximum in the case of Fe_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 . The use of Fe_2O_3 for the purification of coal gas is well known. But the augmenting effect of Al_2O_3 seems to have remained unnoticed—while pure Fe_2O_3 shows an adsorption of 25.54% only and pure Al_2O_3 only 0.36%—a mixed adsorbent containing 25.11% Al_2O_3 shows 56.98% increase in weight due to adsorption of H_2S . An estimation of sulphur in the adsorbent shows that the increase in weight is not due to any foreign substance. It may be noted (Table X) that a maximum amount of sulphur was extracted by solvents from Fe_2O_3 — Al_2O_3 adsorbent.

FIG. 1

It was thought that incorporation of an oxidising agent like MnO_2 with Fe_2O_3 might give even better results than Al_2O_3 . This expectation has not, however, materialised.

In the case of activated charcoal incorporated with alumina, the adsorption was lower than either of Fe_2O_3 — Al_2O_3 or Fe_2O_3 — MnO_2 . In view of the fact that activated carbon is capable of adsorbing H_2S from gases containing traces of this gas and its ability to adsorb organic sulphur (*Chem. Fabric*, 1939, 12, 23), the action of this mixed adsorbent has been further investigated.

Results of Tables I, II, III, IV and V are compared in Fig. 1.

Activation of Various Adsorbents

It will be seen from previous results that lower adsorption is obtained with samples dried below 100°, whereas much higher adsorption is obtained with samples heated to 230°-235°. Evidently moisture plays an important part in determining the activity. The necessity of traces of moisture for adsorption has been noted by various investigators working with silica gel, alumina gel and other adsorbents. In the case of iron oxide ore used for gas refining Avery (*Gas J.*, 1931, 196, 311) maintains that best results can be obtained with samples containing 35-40% moisture while Thomson (*Gas J.*, 1940, 229, 190) recommends 20-25% moisture for the same purpose. The adsorbents used by us have, therefore, been preheated to various temperatures in order to regulate moisture content and their activity determined.

About 15 to 20 g. of the sample were taken in a glass combustion tube which was maintained at the particular temperature for 1½ hours. Dry air was blown in with a Cenco blower through this electrically heated tube at a constant rate. Results are represented in Figs. 2 and 3.

TABLE VI

Adsorbent: $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, containing 25.11% of Al_2O_3 , obtained by simultaneous precipitation.
Time of activation = 1½ hours. $\text{H}_2\text{S} = 2.81\%$ by volume

Temp.	Sulphur content		
	Water content.	Average increase in weight.	Sulphur esti. mated by fusion method.
95°	13.48%	27.40%	27.06%
200°	8.01	52.91	51.72
240-245°	6.86	60.34	59.88
300°	4.98	54.93	54.20
Strong ignition	—	41.95	40.23

In view of the success achieved by $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ mixture, we thought it advisable to investigate the action of bauxite as an adsorbent. For this purpose, two samples of bauxite, obtained through the courtesy of the Director, Geological Survey of India, were studied.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

TABLE V II
Bauxite

Analysis	Sample		Time of activation (1½ hrs.)			
	Sample I. 20'32	Sample II. 20'9	Sample I (H ₂ S in gas = 2'73%)		Sample II (H ₂ S in gas = 2'88%)	
Loss on ignition (%)			Temp.	Sulphur content	Sulphur content	
Al ₂ O ₃	27'8	65'2		Average increase in wt.	Sulphur estimated.	Average Increase in wt.
Fe ₂ O ₃	11'7	1'9				Sulphur estimated.
SiO ₂	11'6	0'34	30-31°	15'48%	14'88%	13'20%
TiO ₂	6'7	11'3	450°	21'48	20'05	17'23
CaO	20'8	Traces	350°	27'26	27'10	20'12
MgO	0'41	Traces	450°	37'49	37'12	27'71
			500°	31'22	31'22	25'83
						24'98

Comparatively low figure of adsorption in the case of these bauxites is perhaps due to a low Fe₂O₃ content in the samples and a comparatively high Al₂O₃ content. Thus sample II with higher Al₂O₃ and lower Fe₂O₃ content than sample I shows a lower adsorption.

It will be seen that the optimum results have been obtained by heating precipitated *iron oxide-alumina* to 240-250° and bauxite to 450°. In the case of bauxite, the organic constituents and excess of moisture have to be removed by heating it to a higher temperature *i.e.* 450°.

Time of contact of the different adsorbents was determined and the results are stated below.

TABLE VIII

Optimum rate of flow

- A. Fe₂O₃-Al₂O₃ with 25'11% Al₂O₃, activated at 230-235° for 1½ hours. H₂S = 3'01% by volume.
- B. Fe₂O₃-MnO₂ with 30'84% MnO₂ activated at 230-235° for 1½ hours. H₂S = 3'1% by volume.
- C. Activated carbon-Al₂O₃ with 14'2% Al₂O₃, activated at 230-235°. H₂S = 2'62% by volume.

Rate of flow (bubbles per min.)	Sulphur content		Sulphur content		Sulphur content	
	Average increase in wt.	Sulphur estimated by fusion method.	Average increase in wt	Sulphur estimated.	Average increase in wt.	Sulphur estimated.
20	55'04%	54'85%	48'26%	48'20%	42'20%	37'80%
30	54'99	54'25	47'94	47'28	41'85	37'70
40	54'92	54'13	46'08	46'00	38'61	36'15
60	53'99	53'78	45'47	45'30	35'77	34'00
80	50'95	50'05	39'87	39'10	31'60	28'06

The relative merits of the different adsorbents can be had from a comparison of the above tables.

Effect of Oxygen present in the Gaseous Mixture

Though adequate quantities of air when mixed with sulphurous industrial gases passing through iron-oxide bed are known to give better results, excess of oxygen may have harmful

effect in that it may cause fusion of sulphur, thereby closing the pores of the adsorbent or even ignition of the gas. Experiments were, therefore, done to get an idea of the optimum proportion of oxygen under a given set of condition. Results are given below.

TABLE IX

Adsorbent used : $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ with 29.83% Al_2O_3 , activated at 230-235° for 1½ hrs.
 H_2S in the gaseous mixture being 2.06% by volume.

Oxygen (by volume).	Sulphur content	
	Average increase in wt.	Sulphur estimated.
1.56%	54.94%	54.24%
2.38	55.25	55.12
3.10	58.68	58.13
4.20	58.72	58.15
5.05	58.88	58.20

The reason for increase of adsorption at 3 to 5% oxygen content is evidently regeneration of iron oxide *in situ* with the liberation of free sulphur.

Recovery of Elementary Sulphur from Adsorbents

Modern processes usually recover sulphur from the spent oxide by extraction with CS_2 (Broche & Net. *Brennst.-Chem.*, 1932, 13, 201, 664). The various adsorbents used by us were, therefore, extracted with carbon disulphide and the elementary sulphur was estimated by evaporation of the solvent.

As combined sulphur is not extracted, we have passed air through the residue after each extraction. The residue was transferred to glass combustion tube and air was passed through it for one hour at the rate of 100 bubbles per minute at room temperature. This would liberate any combined sulphur and would increase the amount of extractable sulphur. The sulphur obtained by extraction is yellowish and is quite pure. Extraction was carried out at ordinary pressure in a Soxhlet and at higher pressure in an autoclave—a higher yield being obtained when pressure is applied. Results are shown below.

TABLE X

Extraction by carbon disulphide

Particulars of adsorbents.	Sulphur in adsorbents.	Manner of extraction.	Sulphur content (%)			Total.
			Before aeration. (1st Extract)	After 1st aeration. (2nd Extract)	After 2nd aeration. (3rd Extract)	
$\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (20.1%) Mechanical mixture.	34.8%	(a) Soxhlet	84.3	4.0	1.1	89.4
		(b) Autoclave (4.5 kg.)	96.7	—	—	96.7
$\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (25.11%) Precipitated from soln.	56.83	(a) Soxhlet	79.20	2.48	1.17	82.75
		(b) Autoclave (4.5 kg.)	93.20	0.56	—	93.66
$\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (25.11%) Precipitated and activated at 240-245°	59.88	(a) Soxhlet	76.82	3.20	0.5	80.42
		(b) Autoclave (4.5 kg.)	90.67	0.20	—	90.87
$\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{MnO}_2$ (34.82%) Precipitated from soln.	53.98	(a) Soxhlet	81.22	2.50	0.82	84.54
		(b) Autoclave (4.5 kg.)	93.86	0.10	—	93.96
Activated carbon- Al_2O_3 (9.28%).	43.98	(a) Soxhlet	61.20	1.20	—	62.20
		(b) Autoclave (4.5 kg.)	68.2	0.1	—	68.3
Baunite—Sample 1	37.12	(a) Soxhlet	22.21	1.80	—	24.01
		(b) Autoclave (4.5 kg.)	28.22	—	—	28.22

It will be found that the extraction of elementary sulphur is quite satisfactory in the cases of $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3-\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3-\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3$. This evidently is due to the formation of free sulphur; the traces of oxygen present in the gas oxidise sulphuretted hydrogen in the presence of alumina, liberating free sulphur which can easily be extracted. A small amount of sulphur adheres, however, tenaciously to the adsorbent and can only be extracted when pressure is employed. The same remarks apply to $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3-\text{MnO}_2$ adsorbent, free elementary sulphur being present in the substance after the passage of the gas.

In the case of activated carbon—alumina, the amount extracted does not seem to be very satisfactory and is 62.2% at ordinary and 68.3% under high pressures. This is due, either to the unsuitability of activated carbon used by us for the purpose or to the sulphur being difficultly extractable. It will be seen that aeration does not appreciably increase the amount of extractable sulphur. In the case of bauxite, only a small percentage of sulphur is extractable with carbon disulphide. It is likely that substances like calcium and magnesium present in bauxite, form stable compounds of sulphur which cannot be extracted. In the case of the three samples of $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3-\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ adsorbent extracted, it will be noticed that there is a gradual fall in the extraction value with the increase in the percentage of sulphur in the adsorbent. Evidently, the higher the sulphur content in the $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3-\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, the lower is the proportion of extracted sulphur. It is probable that in the presence of excess of sulphur, complex sulphides of the type $(\text{FeS}_x, \text{FeS})_x(\text{H}_2\text{O})_y$ are formed which are more stable than simple sulphides and liberate sulphur with difficulty.

Revivification of the Adsorbents

Utility of an adsorbent on an industrial scale will depend to a great extent on whether or not the adsorbent can be revived to its original activity.

(a) $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3-\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ adsorbent.—Stinnes (B.P. 371,117) patented a process for restoring used spent oxide to its former activity by the addition of small quantity of alkaline earth salts. Taking the clue from the above brief report, we have been able to restore $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3-\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ adsorbent after extraction to almost its original activity.

The adsorbent which contained 56.98% sulphur and was extracted under pressure with CS_2 , was intimately mixed with different quantities of calcium carbonate and the mixture heated to a temperature of $230-235^\circ$ in a current of dry air for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The activity, determined in the usual manner, is shown in Table XI.

TABLE XI

Revivified $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3-\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ adsorbent.
 H_2S in gas = 2.63% by volume.

CaCO ₃ used.	Sulphur content	
	Average increase in weight.	Sulphur estimated by fusion method.
0	45.59%	45.13%
4%	50.93	50.16
6	55.96	55.71
8	55.73	55.68

TABLE XII

Sulphur from revivified $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3-\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ adsorbent.
 Sulphur content in the adsorbent = 55.71%.

Manner of extraction.	Percentage of sulphur		
	Before aeration.	After first aeration.	Total.
Soxhlet	80.50	3.20	83.70
Autoclave (4.5 kg.)	93.70	...	93.70

The data shown in Table XII will further show that extraction of sulphur from this revived mass is quite satisfactory and is practically of the same order as the original.

(b) *Activated carbon—Al₂O₃ adsorbent.*—In this case, the used charcoal, after extraction with carbon disulphide was revived with steam, air and traces of ammonia mixture at a temperature of 250°. This method of activating charcoal was recommended by Bakes, King and Sinnatt (*D. S. I. R., Fuel Res. Tech. Paper, No. 31, 1931*). The best results were obtained after passing the above gases for a period of 60 minutes as the following table shows.

TABLE XIII

Revivification of activated carbon—Al₂O₃ adsorbent containing 9.28% Al₂O₃

Sulphur in the adsorbent = 43.98%. H₂S in the gas = 2.28 % by vol. Rate of passing the mixed gases = 100 bubbles per min.

Period of revivification.	Sulphur content	
	Average increase in weight.	Sulphur estimated by Eschka method.
0	25.74%	23.24%
45 mins.	38.50	38.10
60	43.53	43.21
75	43.45	43.15

It will be seen that the original activity is fully restored, the loss in weight during revivification being negligible. It is likely that steam and air act as sweeping or washing out agents and ammonia removes any sulphur compound in the adsorbent by chemical action. A small amount of sulphur compounds retained by the adsorbent is, however, lost during the process.

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